

MICRO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF PRESTRESSED FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The lamination theory analysis of thin laminates was extended to evaluate the fields of stresses in the matrix and the fibers of each k-th ply of a laminated structure by the application of theory elasticity methods of complex variable and analytic functions for non-homogeneous media. It has been shown that composite material structures are self-stressed during manufacture and the detrimental effects of initial, or residual, stress-strain state can be effectively controlled by using pre-tension of prepregs. Prestressed composite material structural elements differ from conventional ones by potentially higher characteristics of strength, stiffness, service life and reliability.

INTRODUCTION

The development of structural analysis of fiber reinforced composite laminates (FRCL) follows the recognition of their real structure. After being considered as anisotropic and quasi-homogeneous at whole, constituent plies in FRCL were taken into consideration and the theories of laminated media have emerged. At the same time methods of microanalysis have been developed and used to evaluate stresses in the matrix and the fibers of uniaxially reinforced composite piles. But until recently these two kinds of analysis (macro and micro) have been used separately and the distribution of stresses in the matrix and the fibers of FRCL under various kind of loading has not been known. The approach for such integrated macro- and microanalysis has been developed and presented here for the analysis of prestressed FRCL.

MICROANALYSIS OF A LAMINATE'S PLY

Each constituent ply of a laminate under loading is considered to be in a plane stress state, under the action of the so-called "mean" stresses, $\langle \sigma_i \rangle$, $i = 1, 2, 6$ (1, 2 - the main axes of the layer). The microanalysis is performed by a successive consideration of each k-th ply under the action of axial load $\langle \sigma_1 \rangle^{(k)}$ transverse load $\langle \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)}$ and longitudinal shear $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ with final superposition of above solutions for the microstress components.

1. Axial loading of a ply

The ply of uniaxially fiber reinforced composite material (FRCL) is considered as a non-homogeneous body with axis X_1 along fiber's orientation, the structure of which (cross-section in plane X_2, X_3) is represented by regular double periodic model with main periods $2\pi\omega_1$, $2\pi\omega_2 e^{i\alpha}$ and the fibers, placed in the nodes of the double periodic net (Fig. 1). The ply under axial loading $\langle \sigma_1 \rangle^{(k)}$ or $\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle^{(k)}$ is considered to be in a plane strain state and the stresses in the regions occupied by the matrix and by the fibers can be found using methods developed by Mushelishvili and some others [1, 2, 3]. The analytic stress functions, or potentials, of a complex variable

were taken to satisfy the requirements of symmetry and periodicity in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_m(z) &= A_0 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_{2n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{2n+2}}{z^{2n+2}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} A_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \alpha_{j,n} z^{2j}; \\ \Psi_m(z) &= B_0 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{2n+2}}{z^{2n+2}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} B_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \alpha_{j,n} z^{2j} - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2n+2) A_{2n+2} \lambda_f \beta_{ij} z^{2j}; \\ \Phi_f(z) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{2n} z^{2n}; \quad \Psi_f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{2n} z^{2n}.\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Here subindexes "m" and "f" refer to the matrix and the fibers, correspondingly.

The exact expressions (1), including unknown coefficients $A_{2n}, B_{2n}, a_{2n}, b_{2n}, n=0,1,3,\dots$, and coefficients $\alpha_{ij}, \beta_{ij}, i,j=0,1,\dots$, are to be found from the boundary conditions and the symmetry of the net under consideration. The boundary conditions at the interface, $z=t$, of centrally located fiber ($m,n=0$) express the equality of stresses and the difference, or "jump", of displacements, correspondingly:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_m(t) + \overline{\Phi_m(t)} - [\bar{t} \Phi_m'(t) + \Psi_m(t)] e^{2i\theta} &= \Phi_f(t) + \overline{\Phi_f(t)} - [\bar{t} \Phi_f'(t) + \Psi_f(t)] e^{2i\theta}, \\ -\alpha_m \overline{\Phi_m(t)} + \Phi_m(t) - [\bar{t} \Phi_m'(t) + \Psi_m(t)] e^{2i\theta} + \frac{G_m^{(k)}}{G_f^{(k)}} \{ \alpha_f \overline{\Phi_f(t)} - \Psi_f(t) + [\bar{t} \Phi_f'(t) + \Psi_f(t)] e^{2i\theta} \} &= -2G_m^{(k)} \langle \epsilon_i \rangle^{(k)} (\nu_f^{(k)} - \nu_m^{(k)}) \lambda_f e^{i\theta}, \quad t \in \Gamma_{0,0}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

Here $\alpha = 3 - 4\nu$ - Muskhelishvili's constant, and λ_f - radius of fibers.

The boundary problem solution (for the symmetry $\alpha = \pi/3$) gives:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_m^{\parallel}(z) &= K \left[\frac{\pi}{4\sqrt{3}} B_2 \lambda_f^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_{6n} \frac{\lambda_f^{6n}}{z^{6n}} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} A_{6n} \lambda_f^{6n} \alpha_{3j,3n-1} z^{6j} \right]; \\ \Psi_m^{\parallel}(z) &= K \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{6n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{6n+2}}{z^{6n+2}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{6n+2} \lambda_f^{6n+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{3j+2,3n} z^{6j+4} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n A_{6n} \lambda_f^{6n} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} B_{3j+2,3n-1} z^{6j+4} \right]; \\ \Phi_f^{\parallel}(z) &= K \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{6n} z^{6n}; \quad \Psi_f^{\parallel}(z) = K \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{6n-2} z^{6n-2}; \quad K = 4G_m \langle \epsilon_i \rangle^{(k)} (\nu_f - \nu_m).\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

The stress components in the fibers and the matrix under axial loading of k-th layer of a laminate can be found in accordance with the formula:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{x;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} &= \operatorname{Re} \left\{ 2\Phi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) - \bar{z} \left[\Phi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right]' - \Psi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right\}, \\ \sigma_{y;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} &= \operatorname{Re} \left\{ 2\Phi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) + \bar{z} \left[\Phi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right]' + \Psi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right\}, \\ \tau_{xy;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} &= \operatorname{Im} \left\{ \bar{z} \left[\Phi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right]' + \Psi_{m,f}^{\parallel}(z) \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

The axial component of the stress field is determined by using formula

$$\sigma_{z; m, f}^{(k)} = E_{m, f}^{(k)} \langle \epsilon_1 \rangle^{(k)} - 4\nu_{m, f} \operatorname{Re} \Phi_{m, f}^{\parallel}(\bar{z}). \quad (5)$$

2. Transverse loading of a ply

The microstress components in the fibers and the matrix of a k-th ply of a laminate under transverse loading $\langle \pm \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)}$ can be found as superposition of two boundary problem solutions for two kinds of symmetric loading: $\langle \pm \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)} = \langle \pm \sigma_3 \rangle^{(k)}$ and $\langle \pm \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)} = \langle \mp \sigma_3 \rangle^{(k)}$

The resulted stress functions have the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_m^{\perp}(\bar{z}) &= \langle \mp \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} A_2 \lambda_f^2 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{2n+2}}{z^{2n+2}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{j, n} z^{2j} - \\ &- \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2n+2) A_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \beta_{ij} z^{2j}; \\ \Phi_m^{\perp}(\bar{z}) &= \frac{\langle \pm \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)}}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4\sqrt{3}} B_2 \lambda_f^2 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_{2n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{2n+2}}{z^{2n+2}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{j, n} z^{2j}; \\ \Phi_f^{\perp}(\bar{z}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{2n} z^{2n}; \quad \Psi_f^{\perp}(\bar{z}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{2n} z^{2n}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The microstress components in the fibers and the matrix of a k-th ply of a laminate under transverse loading $\langle \pm \sigma_2 \rangle^{(k)}$ can be found using formulae (4,5) and stress functions (6).

3. Longitudinal shear loading of a ply

The components of the microstress in the fibers and the matrix of a k-th ply under longitudinal shear $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle^{(k)}$ are determined as follows:

$$\tau_{12; m, f}^{(k)} = 2G_{m, f}^{(k)} \operatorname{Re} \Phi_{m, f}^{\perp}(\bar{z}). \quad (7)$$

The stress functions were determined by the solution of the corresponding boundary problem and finally get the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_m(\bar{z}) &= \frac{\langle \tau_{12} \rangle^{(k)}}{2G_m^{(k)}(1+\nu_f^{(k)})} \bar{z} + A_0 \bar{z} - A_2 \lambda_f^2 \left[\frac{1}{\bar{z}} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \alpha_{j, 0} \frac{\bar{z}^{2j+1}}{2j+1} \right] - \\ &- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_{2n+2}}{2n+2} \frac{\lambda_f^{2n+2}}{z^{2n+1}} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} A_{2n+2} \lambda_f^{2n+2} \alpha_{j, n} \frac{z^{2j+1}}{2j+1}, \\ \Phi_f(\bar{z}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \frac{\bar{z}^{2n-1}}{2n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

4. Integrated microstress field of a k-th ply of a laminate under loading

The summing up of the same components of microstress in the matrix and the fibers of a k-th ply makes it possible to define complete fields of microstresses that formed under plane stress state, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{1;m,f}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\perp(k)} ; & \sigma_{2;m,f}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\perp(k)} ; \\ \sigma_{3;m,f}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\perp(k)} ; & \tau_{23;m,f}^{(k)} &= \tau_{23;m,f}^{\parallel(k)} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\perp(k)} \\ \tau_{12;m,f}^{(k)} &= \tau_{12;m,f}^{(k)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The approach developed can be used for the consideration of combined action of external (mechanical) loading, temperature effects (in production and in service), effects of prestrain in manufacture, humidity in service, etc., together with the most complete set of material, design and manufacture parameters. It can be used as comprehensive tool for prediction and optimization of strength, stiffness, service life and reliability of composite structural elements.

PRESTRAINED STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

The strength analysis performed has shown that the residual thermo-stresses generated in plies, matrix and fibers of FRCL are detrimental to the integrity and, hence, quality, of structural elements. The residual stresses and the integrity of composite material structural elements can be effectively controlled in manufacture by pretension of prepregs and required level of pretension can be defined from integrated macro- and micro-analysis taking into account material, manufacturing and design parameters together with external loading. The resulted microstress components can be summarized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\parallel} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\perp} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\parallel,\perp} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\perp,T} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\parallel,H} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{\perp,H} + \sigma_{1;m,f}^{res} ; \\ \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\parallel} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\perp} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\parallel,\perp} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\perp,T} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\parallel,H} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{\perp,H} + \sigma_{2;m,f}^{res} ; \\ \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\parallel} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\perp} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\parallel,\perp} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\perp,T} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\parallel,H} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{\perp,H} + \sigma_{3;m,f}^{res} ; \\ \tau_{12}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \tau_{12;m,f} + \tau_{12;m,f}^T + \tau_{12;m,f}^H ; \\ \tau_{13}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \tau_{13;m,f} + \tau_{13;m,f}^T + \tau_{13;m,f}^H ; \\ \tau_{23}^{\Sigma T,H,N} &= \tau_{23;m,f}^{\parallel} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\perp} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\parallel,T} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\perp,T} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\parallel,H} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{\perp,H} + \tau_{23;m,f}^{res} . \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Here $\sigma_{i,m,f}^{res}$ - residual thermoelastic stresses generated in isolated unidirectional ply.

Fig. 2 shows the possibilities for the control of thermoelastic residual microstresses in matrix for carbon fiber laminate; by pretension of plies the resulted stress field components can be effectively decreased, depending upon fiber volume in composite.

CONCLUSION

The intergrated macro- and micro-analysis has, for the first time, made possible a comprehensive evaluation of stress fields in the matrix and the fibers of FRCM and structures through their life history under manufacturing; operational and environmental conditions. It can be successfully used for design and optimization of composite material structures relative to material, design and manufacturing variables under given loading conditions.

The integrity of FRCL structures can be effectively improved by the pretension of prepregs in manufacture. The required degree of pretension is to be determined from the analysis, provided that no cracks are present within matrix and plies under given material, manufacturing, loading and environmental conditions. Thus the conception of prestressed FRCM structural elements has been introduced to improve their carrying capacity, service life and reliability.

The comprehensive microstress computerized analysis can be possibly extended to investigate in depth the strength and fracture of FRCM and structures as a function of various design, manufacturing and loading conditions.

REFERENCES

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Fig. 1 Model double-periodic structure of uniaxially reinforced FRSM

Fig. 2 Tangential component of microstress (at the interface of the fiber) in the second ply of carbon fiber laminate:

1, 2, 3, total thermoresidual stresses
 $\lambda_j = 0.75, 0.85, 0.95$, corresp.
 4, 5, 6 - same, but with prestrain
 $\varepsilon_1^p = 0.6$
 ($\bar{\varepsilon}_{pr}$ - prepreg strain limite)

